

E-FIR SYSTEM

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Abstract—E-FIR online web based FIR register system , with the help of this project people can online access and register Fir in his nearest police station in overall India, there are several people cant register Fir because the hectic procedure of fir system and physical appearance .the main purpose of this online Fir system to increase the better interaction common people and police station and decrease the crime rate of India.

Keywords—E-Fir, Police Station

I. INTRODUCTION

Tradition method of the fir registration is to hectic and people hesitate to complaints FIR because normal people avoid the judiciary system they think it time consuming and the lack of transparency. To solve these The problem with introducing the E-Fir System or online Fir is to develop an online crime reporting and operating system which is fluently accessible to the public , the police department and the advanced authority and people easily register online fir with the help of internet devices anywhere and anytime . This system has been proposed keeping in mind the difficulties that people face during enrollment complaints of any police station user being able to register online Fir anywhere and anytime. Original people can Register , Edit, and Status Check and track the filing Fir. Higher Authority check and edit the fir status that for security and completeness of entire procedure

II.LITRECHER REVIEW

- [1] E-FIR using E-Governance, This paper describe that how to conquer the conversation between neighborhood police and people and the better trade among consumer and cops
- [2] Integration of superior e-FIR lading machine with popular medical institution for scientific file generation, This paper describe that the the way to preserve law and order with particular area by using recording the actual crime price
- [3] E-FIR gadget with Chatbot, This paper describe that the triumph over hole among police and local humans
- [4] A Survey on Securing Crime Case precis and E-fir in Police Station, This paper describe to overcome crime rate in modern scenario

III.EXISTING SYSTEM

- Fake Fir - thrilling device of the registration of fir to tense and masses of time check in false instances because the giving of miss statistics of local police
- Time Taking - contemporary procedure of the registration of the FIR it took too much time and one and extra humans to complete paintings.
- missing record - Now the offline fir registration system takes an excessive amount of office work and after a while we're facing protection and facts security troubles.
- anxious technique- the conventional method of the fir registration an excessive amount of annoying there why lots of people hesitate to register fir

- Political stress - the masses of police station police do no longer register the complains of nearby human beings with the political stress

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

- Immediately FIR Registration - customers can effortlessly on the spot registration of FIR with incident location to her nearest police station with the help of an internet device and without bodily appearance.
- Statistics Protection- Database operation gadget for the quickest access and storehouse of your statistics so that the statistics is extra comfortable and strong.
- Advanced Authority - The whole system controlled by using the superior authority, a completely low hazard of missing information and fake fir instances.
- Tracking - once the person registers after that to fluently music the reputation of a primary records report with the assist of any net tool everywhere and each time .
- Transparency- Proposed device became absolutely transparent with the generation of e receipt of every level of complete process.

V. DATA FLOW

Fig 1 Shows the user data flow of our website.

Fig 2 Shows the admin data flow of our website information .

Fig 1 User Data Flow

Fig 2 Admin Data Flow

VI. SCOPE

- Boom Registration - on-line Fir machine website increases the enrollment of fir and reduces the charge of fake fir cases its most useful for the individuals who aren't capable of physically appear .
- look for Crime kind- on-line Fir system with the help of machine learning finds the form of crime and reveals the highest Crime sensitive area.
- Integration- In future on line Fir device integrated with distinct on line structures like E-court docket and E-Governance it really is beneficial to locating crook file and the crime suspect.
- records control - online fir registration batter useful to hold a virtual record for research and greater secure.
- E-Governance - it's miles play crucial role for the better management and conversation of advanced authority, police and the local people

VII. CONCLUSION

The proposed exploration model will help the area people to file online fir anywhere and each time without bodily look of a nearest police station .This may ameliorate the higher integration between nearby people, nearest police station and neighborhood government. E-Fir gadget neighborhood character filing the fir and fluently modifying, View, popularity checking and tracking the submitting Fir. there's a opportunity of submitting false fir cases which might be move verification by the police individual and additionally test documents for authentic identity. those initiatives are also useful for the people who do no longer come ahead because they do not need to interact inside the judicial process .This whole device is absolutely obvious, paperless and controlled with the aid of the superior authority that decreases the faux fir instances.

VIII. RESULT

Fig 1 Shows the home page of our website.

Fig 2 Shows the management of our website information .

Fig 1 Homepage

Fig 2 Dashboard

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